

DEVELOPMENT OF A WEB-BASED VETERINARY CLINIC SERVICE INFORMATION SYSTEM USING THE PROTOTYPE MODEL AT ARTZIMAR PETSHOP

Muhammad Ghoni Khidir Tohir
Information Systems Department
Binus Online, Bina Nusantara
University
Jakarta, 11480, Indonesia
muhammad.tohir@binus.ac.id

Ratih Octavia Rini
Information Systems Department
Binus Online, Bina Nusantara
University
Jakarta, 11480, Indonesia
ratih.rini@binus.ac.id

Aviza Anandya
Information Systems Department
Binus Online, Bina Nusantara
University
Jakarta, 11480, Indonesia
aviza.anandya@binus.ac.id

Silvia Ayunda Murad
Information Systems Department
Binus Online, Bina Nusantara University
Jakarta, 11480, Indonesia
silvia.ayunda@binus.ac.id

ABSTRACT: Petshop Artzimar manages its veterinary clinic services using paid software with non-integrated modules, causing patient data management, appointment scheduling, electronic medical records, and inventory management to run independently of one another. The per-user licensing scheme has driven account-sharing practices that weaken system accountability. This study aims to analyze system requirements, develop a web-based veterinary clinic information system, and evaluate its feasibility against the operational needs of Petshop Artzimar. Development followed Pressman's Prototype model across three iterative cycles, involving three user roles (Customer, Veterinarian, and Admin), built using TypeScript, React, Node.js, Express, and PostgreSQL. The system consolidates all clinic operations into a single centralized database, covering patient management, appointment scheduling, electronic medical records, inventory management, inpatient care, and operational reporting. Black Box Testing across 43 scenarios yielded a success rate of 97.67%. UAT results showed all evaluated aspects scoring above 80%, with Usability and Interface each reaching 92%. The System Usability Scale produced an average score of 75.5, categorized as good. Based on these results, the system is deemed feasible for implementation at Petshop Artzimar.

Keywords: web-based information system, veterinary clinic, prototype model, Black Box Testing, User Acceptance Testing

SDG: 9 - Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure

I. INTRODUCTION

The global pet care industry reached USD 207 billion in 2025 [1], driving increased demand for veterinary clinic services in Indonesia, where the domestic cat population is projected to reach 5.95 million by 2026 [2][3]. This growth requires veterinary clinics to have adequate service

management systems capable of handling rising visit volumes effectively.

Petshop Artzimar is a business operating in both pet product retail and veterinary clinic services. Currently, clinic operations are managed through paid software where the modules are not integrated into a single centralized database. The stock management, doctor scheduling, and inpatient recording modules operate separately, meaning data synchronization across modules cannot be performed automatically and staff must enter the same data multiple times. Furthermore, the annual subscription cost reaches IDR 13,234,794, yet account quota limitations have led one veterinarian to share an account with other users, making it impossible to track each doctor's activity individually and compromising system access accountability.

Similar problems have been identified in prior studies. Non-centralized veterinary clinic management has been linked to difficulties in real-time data access and increased risk of data loss [4]. Web-based systems have demonstrated significant improvements in operational efficiency [5], with one web-based medical records system achieving an effectiveness score of 96% [6]. Integrated digital service systems have also been shown to accelerate service delivery and improve operational workflow efficiency [7]. However, these studies generally cover only a subset of clinic operational functions. Arsad and Pribadi [4] and Pinatih et al. [6] focus on patient management and medical records without addressing inventory management. Rosmani and Mokhtar [8] handle only appointment scheduling, without rescheduling or inpatient features. Ramadhana et al. [7], Syahidah et al. [10], and Abidin and Mohd Yusof [11] do not cover detailed inpatient condition monitoring. Additionally, all of these studies focus on clinics that had not yet adopted any digital system, leaving unaddressed the challenge of module fragmentation in clinics already using paid software with non-integrated modules.

This study addresses that gap by developing a web-based veterinary clinic information system for Petshop Artzimar,

covering appointment reservations, electronic medical records, inventory management, rescheduling with a schedule negotiation mechanism, and inpatient care with role-based patient condition monitoring that includes body temperature, heart rate, and respiration rate recording. The system was developed using Pressman's Prototype model [12] iteratively through the stages of communication, quick plan, modeling quick design, construction of prototype, and deployment, delivery and feedback, and was tested using Black Box Testing and User Acceptance Testing to verify that the system meets functional specifications and end-user requirements

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Several studies have developed web-based veterinary clinic information systems to address unintegrated data management. A web-based veterinary clinic management system built using the Waterfall model with PHP and CodeIgniter demonstrated improvements in operational efficiency and reductions in manual recording errors [4]. A DevOps-based web application for veterinary clinic services using PHP and MySQL showed significant gains in service efficiency [5]. A web-based veterinary medical records system developed with the Waterfall model and tested using Black Box Testing and questionnaires reported an effectiveness score of 96% [6]. Digitalization of patient data management and reservations in a web-based veterinary clinic setting has also been shown to improve operational efficiency and service quality [7].

A separate web-based veterinary clinic information system developed using the Waterfall model successfully integrated patient data management, medical records, and doctor scheduling into a single platform [15]. Another system developed using the Prototype model for a regional government clinic in Ciamis fulfilled all defined functional requirements [16].

Other studies have explored various approaches and feature scopes. An online appointment scheduling platform for veterinary clinics built with the Waterfall model reported an average usability score of 4.93 out of 5 [8]. A veterinary knowledge management platform at the local government level, evaluated using ISO/IEC 25010, reported a usability rating of 4.49 out of 5 [9]. A veterinary health service information system for a government agency developed using RAD successfully digitized previously manual recording processes [10]. A dual-platform web and mobile veterinary clinic management system developed using the Prototype model in a Malaysian context reported that all modules passed testing and functioned according to specification [11].

On the testing side, Black Box Testing is widely used to verify system functionality against defined specifications [2][4][6], while UAT is used to assess system suitability from the user perspective in terms of usability and functionality [7][9][19][20]. System usability is measured using the System Usability Scale (SUS), a standardized ten-item Likert-based instrument producing scores from 0 to 100 [13], with adjectival rating categories developed by Bangor et al. [14]. SUS has been consistently applied in

web-based system evaluations to produce representative assessments of end-user usability [17][18].

Prior studies generally cover only one or two core modules such as medical records [6], scheduling [8], or registration and queuing [7], without integrating them into a single platform, and most were developed using the Waterfall or RAD model [4][6][8][9][10].

Taken together, these studies demonstrate that web-based veterinary clinic information systems consistently improve operational efficiency and reduce reliance on manual processes. However, a gap remains in the development of a system that integrates all clinic operational features into a single platform using the Prototype model within an Indonesian operational context. This study addresses that gap by developing a web-based veterinary clinic service information system using TypeScript, React, Node.js, and PostgreSQL, covering reservations, electronic medical records, inventory management with stock automation, rescheduling, and inpatient care, developed using Pressman's Prototype model [12] and tested using Black Box Testing and UAT [2] based on the System Usability Scale (SUS) [13].

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employed three data collection methods: observation, interviews, and document study. Observation was conducted directly at Petshop Artzimar over two weeks to understand current clinic operational processes. Interviews were conducted with the owner of Petshop Artzimar to identify system requirements and daily operational problems. Document study involved analyzing patient registration forms, medical record cards, and visit reports used in clinic operations.

A mixed-method approach was applied, combining qualitative and quantitative methods. The qualitative approach was used during the requirements analysis phase through direct observation and interviews with the owner, veterinarians, and administrative staff of Petshop Artzimar. The quantitative approach was derived from UAT results measured based on the success rate of each test scenario.

System development followed Pressman's iterative Prototype model, selected because system requirements were not fully defined at the outset and required direct validation from users [7]. The development stages consisted of: (1) Communication, involving initial requirements identification with stakeholders; (2) Quick Plan, covering feature prioritization for the first iteration; (3) Modeling Quick Design, covering interface wireframe design and system workflow; (4) Construction of Prototype, involving iterative development of a functional prototype; and (5) Deployment, Delivery and Feedback, in which the prototype was handed to users for testing and evaluation, with iterations continuing until the system met operational requirements.

Fig. 1 Pressman's Prototype Model (2010)

The system was built using TypeScript and React on the frontend with Tailwind CSS for the user interface, Node.js and Express on the backend, and PostgreSQL as the relational database management system. Deployment was carried out through the Vercel platform using a Serverless Functions architecture, and the entire development process was managed using GitHub as a version control system to ensure all code changes were documented throughout each iteration.

System testing used two methods. Black Box Testing was used to verify that each system function performs according to defined specifications [2], covering all core features including authentication, patient management, reservations, medical records, and inventory management. User Acceptance Testing (UAT) was conducted involving actual users from Petshop Artzimar to assess system suitability against operational requirements [19][20]. UAT used two instruments: a functional questionnaire per actor using a Likert scale (1 to 5) covering usability and feature completeness, and the System Usability Scale (SUS) to measure overall system usability [13][14].

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Based on requirements analysis and three prototype development iterations, the Petshop Artzimar veterinary clinic information system was successfully built with a centralized database integrating all clinic service processes. This web-based system is consistent with prior findings that web-based systems significantly improve veterinary clinic operational efficiency [4][5]. Two critical features -- rescheduling and inpatient care -- were only identified during the second iteration through direct user feedback, confirming that the Prototype model is effective when user requirements are not fully defined at the outset [12].

A. Proposed System Design

As a solution to the identified problems, a web-based information system was proposed with five main points: centralized database integration, electronic medical records digitalization, an integrated reservation system, medicine management and reporting automation, and navigation connectivity to the existing pet food website through a redirect mechanism.

The system was designed with 21 functional requirements involving three main actors. Table 1 presents a selection of key functional requirements that formed the basis of development.

TABLE 1 FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

FR ID	Module	Description	Actor
FR 3	Medical Records	The system displays an animal's medical records accessible only by its owner	Customer
FR 7	Reservation	Reservation verification is performed by the Veterinarian with a decision to accept or reject accompanied by a reason	Veterinarian
FR 9	Medical Records	The Veterinarian inputs a prescription and the system automatically updates stock	Veterinaria, System
FR 10	Inventory	The system displays a warning to the Admin when medicine stock reaches the minimum threshold	System, Admin
FR 15	Rescheduling	The Veterinarian can propose a reschedule up to three times with a stated reason	Veterinaria, System
FR 17	Inpatient Care	The Veterinarian can initiate the inpatient process after an appointment is confirmed	Veterinarian

B. System Development Design

System development followed Pressman's Prototype model iteratively across three cycles, each involving direct evaluation by user representatives. Each iteration produced feature additions based on feedback obtained from the previous cycle.

Initial Design: Covered the core system features: patient data management, appointment scheduling, electronic medical records, inventory management, and dashboard-based operational reporting. The scheduling feature only supported appointment creation and cancellation, inventory management did not yet include minimum stock thresholds, and the inpatient feature was not yet available. Requirements and initial design artifacts in the form of a Use Case Diagram and ERD were agreed upon with stakeholders as the basis for prototype construction.

Iteration 1: Added search and pagination functionality across all modules. User evaluation feedback identified three unmet needs: recording of appointment cancellation reasons, a rescheduling mechanism, and minimum stock alerts in inventory management.

Iteration 2: Implemented mandatory cancellation reason input, a rescheduling feature with a schedule negotiation mechanism, stock management with minimum thresholds and alert notifications, and file-based bulk data upload. Evaluation feedback identified the need for an inpatient feature that had not been covered in the initial design.

Iteration 3: Implemented the Active Ward feature and role-based inpatient monitoring covering patient body temperature, heart rate, and respiration rate recording. The final evaluation confirmed that the system met operational requirements and was ready to proceed to the testing phase.

C. System Implementation

The system covers three role-based portals for Customers, Veterinarians, and Admins, each tailored to the needs of the respective actor. All actors pass through a login page before accessing their designated portal.

Fig. 2 Login Page

The Customer portal allows customers to add pets, make appointment reservations, and view the medical records of each registered pet. To access the reservation and medical records features, a customer must have an active account and at least one registered pet.

Fig. 3 Customer Portal

On the appointments page, customers can monitor the status of all appointments, covering Pending, Confirmed, Rescheduled, Finished, and Cancelled statuses. The system displays the schedule proposed by the veterinarian along with options to accept the new time or propose a different one, allowing the rescheduling process to be completed directly through the Customer portal.

Fig. 4 Customer Appointment Page

The Veterinarian portal allows veterinarians to confirm appointments, admit patients to inpatient care, and write medical records. Veterinarian accounts must be registered in advance by the Admin.

Fig. 5 Veterinarian Portal

The Active Ward page allows veterinarians to monitor all inpatient patients in real time. Each patient card displays the cage number, condition status (Stable, Recovering, or Critical), owner name, and reason for admission. Veterinarians can record and monitor patient vital data including heart rate, respiration rate, and body temperature through a Vitals Timeline chart, and move patients to the discharge history once treatment is complete.

Fig. 6 Active Ward Page - Veterinarian Portal

The Admin portal allows clinic staff or administrators to view insights and analytics on clinic activity, add veterinarians, and add medical items to inventory.

Fig. 7 Admin Portal

The Clinic Inventory page displays all medical items available in the clinic along with low stock alert notifications for items that fall below the defined minimum threshold. Admins can add new items individually or through CSV file-based bulk upload, and can search and filter items using the Advanced Filter feature.

Fig. 8 Clinic Inventory Page - Admin Portal

D. Testing

Two testing methods were applied in this study: Black Box Testing and User Acceptance Testing.

Black box Testing

Black Box Testing was carry out to verify that each functional feature of the application performs according to user requirements without examining the underlying code directly.

TABLE 2 TEST CASE BLACK BOX TESTING

No	Test Case Description	Expected Result	Actual Result
1	The clinic page displays service information consistent with Petshop Artzimar's visual identity	The page displays the clinic name, services, and visual elements (logo, colors, font) consistent with Petshop Artzimar's identity	The page successfully displayed the clinic name, services, and visual elements (logo, colors, font) consistent with Petshop Artzimar's identity
...
43	The customer can view limited inpatient information for their own pet	The page displays: cage, attending veterinarian, care notes, and condition status (without other sensitive medical data)	The page successfully displayed: cage, attending veterinarian, care notes, and condition status (without other sensitive medical data)

Black Box Testing was conducted across 43 scenarios covering all core system features. Results showed that 42 out of 43 scenarios passed according to defined functional specifications, yielding a success rate of 97.67% [2]. One scenario was recorded as pass with note, indicating the scenario executed as expected but with a minor behavioural note that does not affect core functionality: the reason field in the rescheduling feature was flagged for requiring mandatory input despite being intended as optional.

TABLE 3 BLACK BOX TESTING SUMMARY

Status	Number of Test Case
Passed	42
Passed with note	1
Total Test Case	43

User Acceptance Testing (UAT)

User Acceptance Testing was carry out to verify that the developed system meets user requirements and functions in accordance with expected business processes. Testing involved five respondents consisting of one Admin, two Veterinarians, and two Customers. Results from the functional questionnaire per actor indicated that all features were rated as easy to use and aligned with the operational needs of each role [19][20].

TABLE 4 UAT ASPECT PERCENTAGE SUMMARY

Aspect	Percentage
<i>Usability</i>	92%
<i>Functionality</i>	87%
<i>Information Quality</i>	85%
<i>Interface</i>	92%

The Usability aspect scored 92%, indicating that the system is easy to understand and use. The Functionality aspect scored 87%, indicating that system features and functions performed according to user needs. The Information Quality aspect scored 85%, indicating that the information presented is sufficiently relevant, clear, and understandable, though there remains room for improvement. The Interface aspect scored 92%, indicating that the system's visual design was rated as attractive, consistent, and effective in supporting user interaction.

System Usability Scale (SUS)

Testing was conducted involving three user types: Customer, Veterinarian, and Admin. Each respondent tested the system according to their access rights and available features.

TABLE 5 TEST RESPONDEN

Responden	Inisial
Admin	R1
Customer 1	R2
Customer 2	R3
Dokter 1	R4
Dokter 2	R5

After using the system, respondents were asked to complete the SUS questionnaire consisting of 10 statements rated on a scale of 1 to 5, ranging from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree.

TABLE 6 SUS CATEGORIZATION

Score	Adjective Ratings	Acceptability Ranges	Grade Scale
90-100	Best Imaginable	Acceptable	A
80-89	Excellent	Acceptable	B
70-79	Good	Acceptable	C
62-69	OK	Marginal	D
50-61	OK	Marginal Low	D
35-49	Poor	Not Acceptable	F
25-34	Worst Imaginable	Not Acceptable	F
0-24	Worst Imaginable	Not Acceptable	F

SUS scores range from 0 to 100 and can be interpreted using the adjectival rating categorization scale [14].

TABLE 7 SYSTEM USABILITY SCALE (SUS) TEST RESULTS

Resp.	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10
R1	5	5	4	2	4	3	4	3	5	4
R2	5	4	4	3	5	2	4	3	5	4
R3	5	2	4	1	5	1	4	1	4	1
R4	5	3	4	2	4	2	4	3	5	3
R5	5	3	4	1	4	1	4	1	4	1

SUS scores were then calculated to obtain the system usability value, which serves as a reference for determining the level of feasibility and user acceptance of the application.

TABLE 8 SUS CALCULATION RESULTS

User	SUS Score
Admin	62,5
Customer 1	67,5
Customer 2	90
Dokter Hewan 1	72,5
Dokter Hewan 2	85
Total SUS Score	3
Average SUS Score	75,5

Usability measurement using SUS produced an average score of 75.5, categorized as good [14]. This is reflected in the high respondent agreement on ease of use statements and low agreement on negative statements related to system complexity [13][17][18].

V. CONCLUSION

This study confirms that a web-based veterinary clinic information system can be developed iteratively using the Prototype model to replace non-integrated paid software, with results well received by users. The prototype approach proved effective in accommodating critical features not identified at the outset, such as rescheduling and inpatient care, without overhauling the entire system design. Black

Box Testing across 43 scenarios yielded a success rate of 97.67%, with one scenario recorded as pass with note related to optional field validation in the rescheduling feature. Usability measurement using SUS produced an average score of 75.5, categorized as good [13][14]. UAT results showed an overall average of 89%, confirming that the system meets user needs across usability, functionality, information quality, and interface aspects [20]. Based on these results, the system is deemed feasible for implementation at Petshop Artzimar.

For future research, integrating automated notifications, developing a mobile application, and testing the system in clinics with larger operational scales would strengthen the generalizability of these findings.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to thank Petshop Artzimar for their cooperation throughout this research, including providing access for observation, sharing operational data, and participating in all prototype evaluation and User Acceptance Testing sessions. The authors also extend their appreciation to the veterinarians, administrative staff, and customers who contributed their time and feedback during the system evaluation process.

REFERENCES

- [1] Euromonitor International, "Pet Care Market Experiences Shift as 'Feline Favouritism' Drives Growth," Nov. 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.euromonitor.com/newsroom/press-releases/november-2025/pet-care-market-experiences-shift-as-feline-favouritism-drives-growth>
- [2] ISTQB, "Certified Tester Foundation Level Syllabus," 2024.
- [3] Universitas Gadjah Mada, "Jumlah Hewan Peliharaan Meningkatkan, Mahasiswa UGM Bikin Alat Inkubator Cerdas untuk Perawatan," Oct. 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://ugm.ac.id/id/berita/jumlah-hewan-peliharaan-meningkat-mahasiswa-ugm-bikin-alat-inkubator-cerdas-untuk-perawatan>
- [4] B. R. Arsad and S. S. Pribadi, "Perancangan Sistem Informasi Manajemen Klinik Hewan Berbasis Web Pada Homey Pet Care," *Jurnal Ilmu Komputer Dan Sistem Informasi (JIKOMSI)*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 349–358, 2024, doi: 10.55338/jikoms.v7i2.3848.
- [5] H. Sirajuddin and M. Rusdi, "Perancangan Aplikasi Pelayanan Pada Klinik Hewan Berbasis Web Menggunakan Model DevOps (Development Dan Operation)," *Technologia: Jurnal Ilmiah*, 2024, doi: 10.31602/TJI.V15I2.14359.
- [6] P. H. M. Pinatih, I. A. K. N. I. Nandasari, I. P. G. A. Sudiatmika, and I. N. B. Pramarta, "Sistem Informasi Rekam Medis Klinik Hewan (Studi Kasus: Klinik Hewan Drh. I Dewa Made Anom)," *Jurnal Sutasoma*, 2022, doi: 10.58878/SUTASOMA.V11I1.175.

- [7] A. Ramadhana, D. Moh, Q. A'yun, U. A. Rosyidah, and H. A. Al Faruq, "Service Information System at Kiyowo Vet Jember Animal Clinic," *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence and Information Technology (JAIIT)*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 1–9, 2025, [Online]. Available: <https://publish.umam.edu.my/index.php/ijaiit/article/view/47>
- [8] A. F. Rosmani and M. H. Mokhtar, "An Online Scheduling Platform for Veterinary Appointments," *Jurnal Intelek*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 16–26, 2023, [Online]. Available: <https://ir.uitm.edu.my/id/eprint/82837/>
- [9] K. M. Malicdem and B. L. Lamadrid, "SMART Vet: A Knowledge Management Platform Application for Enhancing Local Government Unit Veterinary Services," *Research and Extension Journal*, vol. 9, no. 1, 2025, doi: 10.62960/DMMMSU.V9I1.74.
- [10] K. Syahidah, S. Esabella, and E. Mardinata, "Sistem Informasi Pelayanan Kesehatan Hewan Pada Klinik Dinas Peternakan Dan Kesehatan Hewan Kabupaten Sumbawa Berbasis Web," *Management of Information System Journal*, vol. 2, 2024, doi: 10.47065/MIS.V2I3.1424.
- [11] M. Z. Abidin and M. Mohd Yusof, "Veterinary Clinic Management Application System," *Applied Information Technology and Computer Science*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 632–648, 2022, [Online]. Available: <https://publisher.uthm.edu.my/periodicals/index.php/aitcs/article/view/2344>
- [12] R. S. Pressman and B. R. Maxim, *Software Engineering: A Practitioner's Approach*, 9th ed. McGraw-Hill Education, 2020.
- [13] J. Brooke, "SUS: A Quick and Dirty Usability Scale," in *Usability Evaluation in Industry*, 1995, p. 189.
- [14] A. Bangor, P. Kortum, and J. Miller, "Determining what individual SUS scores mean: Adding an adjective rating scale," *J. Usability Stud.*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 114–123, 2009.
- [15] S. Handayani, J. Prayoga, and B. S. Hasugian, "Sistem Informasi Klinik Hewan Monsabel Pet's Clinic," *Device: Journal of Information System, Computer Science and Information Technology*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 33–43, 2023, doi: 10.46576/device.v4i1.3438.
- [16] A. Silvia and S. Safitri, "An Information System Design Development 'OKE ANIMAL' for Animal Clinic DISNAKKAN Kabupaten Ciamis Using The Prototype Method," *Journal of Informatics Information System Software Engineering and Applications (INISTA)*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 52–62, 2024, doi: 10.20895/inista.v6i1.1300.
- [17] H. Rachmi and S. Nurwahyuni, "Pengujian Usability Lokamedia Website Menggunakan System Usability Scale," *Al-Khidmah*, vol. 1, no. 2, p. 86, 2018, doi: 10.29406/al-khidmah.v1i2.1155.
- [18] D. W. Ramadhan, "Pengujian Usability Website Time Excelindo Menggunakan System Usability Scale (SUS)," *JUPI (Jurnal Ilmiah Penelitian dan Pembelajaran Informatika)*, vol. 4, no. 2, p. 139, 2019, doi: 10.29100/jipi.v4i2.977.
- [19] H. Yakub, B. Daniawan, A. Wijaya, and L. Damayanti, "Sistem Informasi E-Commerce Berbasis Website Dengan Metode Pengujian User Acceptance Testing," *Jurnal Sistem Informasi Teknik Informatika dan Komputer*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 113–127, Apr. 2024.
- [20] Aliyah, N. Hartono, and A. A. Muin, "Penggunaan User Acceptance Testing (UAT) Pada Pengujian Sistem Informasi Pengelolaan Keuangan Dan Inventaris Barang," *Switch*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 42–58, Mar. 2025.